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Evaluation of the digital environment

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report briefly presents and discusses the evaluation results regarding the use of tools for communicating and document sharing available to the OIKONET partners during the project.

The evaluation was done through different activities:

- 1) at the end of the project's first year, data was collected from all project partners through an on-line survey in order to understand how much the different tools had been used, how useful they were, and to gather suggestions for improving their use;
- 2) two analyses of the actual usages of the various tools were carried out at the half (m18) and at the end (m36) of the project;
- 3) an analysis of the usability of the OIKONET web portal was performed at the end of the second year of the project (m24).

The tools that have been considered in this report are the project website and newsletter, e-mail, Dropbox, Google Docs, Facebook page and groups, Google+ community, Twitter, YouTube, and blogs. The use of these tools has been evaluated according to three different criteria: 1) receiving / getting information about the project, 2) communicating and collaborating with project partners and students, and 3) promoting the project to the outside.

The results show that, generally speaking, partners were satisfied with the available tools. During the project both good practices and issues that needed to be improved and/or fixed emerged:

- Project partners found that **too many communication tools** were initially in use, thus making it difficult to understand which tools were used for which purposes. They suggested selecting fewer tools and using of each of them for a specific function.
- **To get information about the project and to communicate with partners and students, e-mail, the project website and Dropbox** were the most used tools as well as those considered most useful; on the contrary, social networks have been used only by few partners and considered as not very useful for these purposes.
- A clear misalignment emerges when it came to the use of social networks for **promotion** activities: on the one side, **social networks** were considered as very useful for these activities, on the other side only few partners used them.
- During the **major project's events**, such as the international workshops and the international conferences, **peaks in the online communication activities** could be clearly seen, in terms of visits to the project website, engagement of people on the Facebook page, dissemination of activities by project partners in the event-related blogs and in the project Twitter channel, and so on.
- Several **good practices** regarding communication and collaboration for specific project tasks (e.g., learning activities) emerged during the project: in addition to the above mentioned blogs, also **Facebook groups** and **YouTube videos** related to specific learning spaces have been successfully used as a support to the learning experience, or as a promotion and dissemination tool.
- The **usability analysis** helped **identify some critical aspects of the web communication** of the project, such as the excessive amount of textual information available on the homepage, the content structure that in some cases was not clear, and others; the findings of the analysis were used to **refine and update the website**.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and target group

According to the project description, the reports of Deliverable 6.4 “will present the main results of the evaluation of the application of the different learning environments integrated in the OIKONET digital platform. They will provide suggestions to improve the effectiveness of future learning workspaces. The evaluation of the digital environment will focus on both its usability and its actual usages”.

However, in this report the evaluation of the digital platform focused not only on digital learning environments, but mainly on communication and document sharing tools that have been adopted and made available to all the project partners. As a matter of fact, these tools play a fundamental role in the project, as they have to facilitate communications and information and document exchanges within a large consortium.

The evaluation of the tools used in the project was done in different ways:

- 1) An on-line survey sent to all project partners at the end of the first year of the project, aimed at assessing partners’ satisfaction regarding the proposed tools and their perception of usefulness of the tools used. Furthermore, partners were asked how much they used each of the tools, and whether they had suggestions for improving communication and document sharing among partners.
- 2) Two analyses of the actual usages of the communication and document sharing tools, performed at the half (m18) and at the end (m36) of the project. The analyses were done based on different indicators, such as the number of accesses and visits to the website, the number of likes to the Facebook pages and their posts, the number of favourites and re-tweets on the Twitter channel, the number of views of videos on the YouTube channel, and so on.
- 3) An analysis of the usability of the OIKONET digital environment, performed at the end of the second year of the project (m24). The usability analysis was done adopting the approach of user testing: all project partners were asked to perform at least one test in their own institution, following a specific procedure; furthermore, at USI the analysis has been conducted using an eye-tracking tool.

The following tools have been considered in this report:

- E-mail
- Newsletter
- Website
- Dropbox
- Google Docs
- Facebook
- Google+
- Twitter
- YouTube
- Blogs

The target group that has been involved in this evaluation is composed by all project partners, as all of them have been invited to fill in the online survey.

2.2 Contribution of partners

As leader of WP6 Quality Assurance, USI has been responsible for the creation and the publication of the evaluation questionnaire, for the analysis of the received feedbacks, for the analysis of the actual usages of all the communication and document sharing tools, and for the creation of the procedure and the analysis of the results of the evaluation of the usability of the OIKONET web portal.

Leandro Madrazo, as project coordinator and leader of WP5 Digital Platform, has collaborated in the review of this report.

2.3 Relations to other activities in the project

As the use of the communication and document sharing tools that have been analysed and evaluated regard all the project members, the whole OIKONET project can be concerned by this report.

2.4 Abbreviations

- WP stands for **Work Package**.

3 RESULTS OF THE SURVEY

As the OIKONET consortium is quite large (34 partners), one of the major challenges of the project is to have all partners well informed and aligned, to have all of them collaborate in multiple directions and purposes (in the three sub-networks and across them) and work together mostly at distance, because in presence meetings are planned every four/six/twelve months. Thus, three main communication goals have been identified as relevant for the project: 1) receiving / getting information about the project, 2) communicating and collaborating with project partners and students, and 3) promoting the project towards the outside.

A survey was prepared to get feedback from partners about the tools they used and considered useful for these three communication goals. All project members were invited to fill in the survey sent on November 24, 2014. As of January 27, 2015, 25 members answered it (23 completed it, 12 female and 11 male). For each tool, respondents had to say how much they had used it in the first year of the project and how useful they found it with respect to the three goals. Respondents were then asked to give suggestions on how to improve communication and collaboration in the project team.

In this section the results of the survey are presented, structured according to the three abovementioned goals.

3.1 Getting information about the project

The first communication goal that has been identified is to allow all partners to easily get, receive or find information about the project.

The following tools were expected to facilitate the sharing of information related to the project among all partners and were thus adopted during the first year: e-mail, website, newsletter, Dropbox, Google Docs, Facebook (page and groups), Google+, Twitter, YouTube, and blogs.

The following table shows how many respondents have used those tools:

Table 1. Use of the different communication and document sharing tools to get information about OIKONET

Tool	daily	weekly	monthly	less than once	
				per month	never
E-mail	6	15	4	0	0
Website	0	10	8	6	1
Dropbox	1	15	6	1	0
Facebook	1	6	1	8	7
Google+	0	2	5	7	9
Twitter	0	3	1	5	14
YouTube	0	2	0	10	11
Blogs	0	4	1	9	9
Google Docs	0	8	7	8	0

The following graph shows how much those tools are considered useful to get information about the project:

Figure 1. Perceived usefulness of the different communication and sharing tools to get information about the project

As shown in the graph, the same tools that have been **used more frequently to get information about the project** have also been **evaluated as the most useful** for the same purpose: **e-mail, website, Dropbox**.

On the contrary, all **social networking tools** are rarely used by project partners to get information about the project, and are also perceived as not very useful for that purpose.

3.2 Communicating and collaborating with partners and students

When it comes to the tools used most frequently and considered most useful to communicate and collaborate with project partners and students, the situation is very similar to the above: the **most used** tools are **e-mail, Dropbox and Google Docs**; these are also the tools that are perceived as the **most useful** for this purpose.

Also in this case, **social networking tools** are **used very rarely** and considered as **not very useful**.

Table 2. Use of the different tools to communicate and collaborate with colleagues and students

Tool	daily	weekly	monthly	less than once	
				per month	never
E-mail	0	12	7	6	0
Facebook	0	2	2	6	13
Google+	0	1	3	8	11
Twitter	0	1	1	3	18
YouTube	0	1	1	7	14
Blogs	0	1	3	4	15
Dropbox - edited	0	3	13	7	0
Google Docs	0	2	9	10	2

Figure 2. Perceived usefulness of the different tools to communicate and collaborate with colleagues and students.

3.3 Disseminating OIKONET

When it comes to the use of communication tools to disseminate OIKONET activities, the situation is different: the tools that have been **used the most** by project partners are **e-mail and the project website**, while **social networking tools** have been **used rarely** also for this purpose (see Table 3).

Table 3. Use of the different tools to promote the OIKONET project.

Tool	less than once				
	daily	weekly	monthly	per month	never
E-mail	0	1	11	11	2
Website	0	1	9	12	2
Facebook	0	1	4	5	13
Google+	0	0	1	7	15
Twitter	0	1	1	2	19
YouTube	0	0	3	5	15
Blogs	0	0	4	6	13

However, in this case, **social networking tools** are perceived (together with the **website**) as the **most useful tools to promote** the project, especially **Facebook and YouTube**:

Figure 3. Perceived usefulness of the different tools to promote OIKONET

This shows that there is a clear gap between what partners use and what they consider useful to disseminate the project: social networks are considered the most useful tool but they are not used by project partners for this purpose.

This emerges clearly also from some of the comments that respondents added to their answers:

- “Unluckily I don’t have the habit to use Facebook often for job reason (more often for entertainment)”;
- “The use of Facebook at the moment is not much on the network but it has a big potential for the partners/students communication”;
- “In general I don’t use Facebook too much, so I am not used to it”;
- “I still haven’t forced myself to use Google+”;

- “I think that all these tools are very useful, I hope that I will start to get more used to them”;
- “I think YouTube is useful. My fault if I haven’t opened it”.
- “I hope we can share more information through YouTube”.

3.4 Comments and suggestions

Other comments highlight both positive and critical aspects regarding the use of specific communication tools:

- 2 respondents stressed the fact that the **blog** about the Lisbon workshop was useful to understand the development of the learning activities.
- 6 respondents reported to have problems with **Dropbox**, due to its storage size limits; 2 respondents suggested to re-organize the documents in Dropbox and to make clearer where the different information can be found.
- 3 respondents complained about the fact that too many **e-mails** are sent.
- 2 respondents found the **website** too slow and too full of information on the first page; one respondent suggested that the website should be disseminated more often; one respondent found that the website has a good and clear structure, where the materials can be found easily.
- 2 respondents stressed the difference between the OIKONET **Facebook page** and the **Facebook private groups** that have been created to support specific activities (e.g., learning spaces with students, collaboration in work packages): while the Facebook page aims at promoting the project to the outside, the Facebook groups have the goal to support interactions and collaborations in specific project activities.
- 2 respondents found that there is no need to have both **Facebook and Google+**, as they have similar functions.

Project partners were also explicitly asked whether the chosen tools were used in an efficient way and whether they efficiently supported communication. Generally speaking, project partners found that the chosen tools were used efficiently and supported communication. However, 10 respondents found that **too many tools** are in use, thus making it difficult to understand which tools are used for which purposes. Some respondents suggested selecting only some of the tools that are currently in use and agreeing on the most appropriated function of each.

Although most participants found – for the above mentioned reasons – that there is no need to add new tools to improve communications and document sharing, 2 respondents mentioned **LinkedIn** as a tool that might be useful to engage the professional community.

Other respondents suggested other tools, such as mind maps, Box or OneDrive instead of Dropbox, EU communication and networking tools, e-mail notifications of messages in the bulletin boards of each active workspace to all WP4 partners.

4 ANALYSIS OF USAGES

The usage analysis of the adopted communication and document sharing tools focused on the following tools:

- OIKONET website
- OIKONET blogs
- OIKONET newsletter
- OIKONET Facebook page
- OIKONET Twitter channel
- OIKONET YouTube channel
- OIKONET Google+ community

For each of these tools, different indicators have been considered, depending on the available data.

4.1 OIKONET website

The OIKONET website (www.oikonet.org) went online on December 19, 2013.

4.1.1 First half of the project (until February 28, 2015)

According to Google Analytics, in the period from December 19, 2013 to February 28, 2015 the website has been visited by **3454 users** in **7420 different sessions**, for a total of **21'469 pageviews** (on average, 2.89 pages have been viewed in each session).

Fig. 4. Overview of the visits to the OIKONET website (December 19, 2013 – February 28, 2015) (source: Google Analytics)

Some peaks in the visits to the website can be easily recognised in some weeks:

- March 2-8, 2014 (111 visitors, 202 sessions);
- April 6-12, 2014 (**169 visitors**, 216 sessions);
- July 13-19, 2014 (147 visitors, **273 sessions**);
- September 21 – October 4, 2014 (320 visitors, 506 sessions in two weeks);
- February 22-28, 2015 (131 visitors, 217 sessions).

Some of these peaks correspond to important events in the OIKONET project: a new release of the website (March 3, 2014), the Lisbon workshop (July 14-19, 2014), and the first International Conference and first general meeting (Barcelona, September 25-27, 2014).

As it can be seen from the following table, the OIKONET website has been **visited mainly by users coming from Spain**, followed by **Serbia, Portugal** and other partner countries. Interestingly, the website has been visited also by **202 users from Brazil**, although there are no Brazilian partners in the project.

Table 4. Overview of the countries from where users visited the OIKONET website (December 19, 2013 – February 28, 2015) (source: Google Analytics)

Country ?	Acquisition		
	Sessions ? ↓	% New Sessions ?	New Users ?
	7,420 % of Total: 100.00% (7,420)	46.58% Avg for View: 46.48% (0.20%)	3,456 % of Total: 100.20% (3,449)
1. Spain	2,077 (27.99%)	38.28%	795 (23.00%)
2. Serbia	737 (9.93%)	36.09%	266 (7.70%)
3. Portugal	680 (9.16%)	35.29%	240 (6.94%)
4. Slovakia	347 (4.68%)	35.73%	124 (3.59%)
5. Belgium	267 (3.60%)	50.56%	135 (3.91%)
6. Turkey	252 (3.40%)	44.05%	111 (3.21%)
7. Croatia	243 (3.27%)	68.31%	166 (4.80%)
8. United Kingdom	217 (2.92%)	35.02%	76 (2.20%)
9. Brazil	203 (2.74%)	99.51%	202 (5.84%)
10. Italy	185 (2.49%)	70.81%	131 (3.79%)

Most of the visits to the website have been made through a desktop PC (90.1%), while the remaining sessions have been made through mobile phones (467 sessions, 6.3%) or tablets (266 sessions, 3.6%), mainly Apple iPad (250 sessions) or iPhone (239).

The traffic to the OIKONET website has been generated mainly by organic search on internet search engines (41.4% of the traffic, 3071 sessions), followed by direct accesses to the website (30.0%, 2226 sessions), referrals (23.3%, 1729 sessions), and social networks (5.3%, 394 sessions).

Figure 5. Overview of the sources of traffic for the OIKONET website (December 19, 2013 – February 28, 2015) (source: Google Analytics)

Among the social networks, the traffic to the OIKONET website has been generated almost completely by Facebook (221 sessions) and Google+ (130 sessions), while Twitter has generated 31 sessions, Blogger 9 sessions, and LinkedIn 3 sessions.

The following table presents the list of the 10 most viewed pages of the website:

Table 5. List of the most viewed pages of the OIKONET website (December 19, 2013 – February 28, 2015) (source: Google Analytics)

Page	Pageviews	% Pageviews
1. /	6,797	31.66%
2. /index.php/admin_controller/project	1,753	8.17%
3. /index.php/admin_controller/partners	1,636	7.62%
4. /index.php/admin_controller/index	1,393	6.49%
5. /index.php/admin_controller/workshops	1,104	5.14%
6. /index.php/admin_controller/activities	1,102	5.13%
7. /index.php/admin_controller/consortium	1,053	4.90%
8. /index.php/admin_controller/getElement/39/workshop	1,049	4.89%
9. /index.php/admin_controller/conferences	856	3.99%
10. /index.php/admin_controller/getElement/54/conference	499	2.32%

4.1.2 Second half of the project (March 2015 – May 2016)

According to Google Analytics, in the period from March 1, 2015 to May 31, 2016 the website has been visited by **4873 users** in **9650 different sessions**, for a total of **29'422 pageviews** (on average, 3.05 pages have been viewed in each session). Data until May 31, 2016 have been considered (and not until the end of the project), because data from Google Analytics are available until June 7, 2016, due to a change of server.

Fig. 6. Overview of the visits to the OIKONET website (March 1, 2015 – May 31, 2016)
(source: Google Analytics)

As it can be seen from Figure 6, in the second half of the project, the visits to the OIKONET website have been more regular, if compared to the first half: there are no high peaks visible, but visits are more numerous than in the first half and better distributed along the 15 months.

As it can be seen from Table 5, the OIKONET website has been **visited mainly by users coming from Spain**, followed by **Russia, Turkey** and other partner countries.

Table 6. Overview of the countries from where users visited the OIKONET website
(March 1, 2015 – May 31, 2016) (source: Google Analytics)

Country ?	Acquisition
	Sessions ? ↓
	9,650 % of Total: 100.00% (9,650)
1. Spain	2,475 (25.65%)
2. Russia	860 (8.91%)
3. Turkey	730 (7.56%)
4. Germany	615 (6.37%)
5. United Kingdom	441 (4.57%)
6. Ireland	427 (4.42%)
7. Slovakia	386 (4.00%)
8. Portugal	286 (2.96%)
9. Serbia	275 (2.85%)
10. Belgium	262 (2.72%)

As in the first half of the project, most of the visits to the website have been made through a desktop PC (89.7%), while the remaining sessions have been made through mobile phones (734 sessions, 7.6%) or tablets (262 sessions, 2.7%), mainly Apple iPhone (371 sessions) or iPad (200). If compared to the first 18 months of the project, a small increase in the use of mobile phones can be noticed (from 6.3% to 7.6%).

The traffic to the OIKONET website has been generated mainly by organic search on internet search engines (46.2% of the traffic, 4458 sessions), followed by referrals (27.3%, 2635 sessions), direct accesses to the website (22.4%, 2159 sessions), and social networks (4%, 390 sessions).

Figure 7. Overview of the sources of traffic for the OIKONET website (March 1, 2015 – May 31, 2016) (source: Google Analytics)

If compared to the first half of the project, the traffic generated by organic searches and by referrals has increased, while direct accesses to the website have decreased; this can be seen as a signal that the website has been able to attract more external people.

Traffic generated by social networks has remained very low also in the second half of the project; among them, traffic has been generated almost completely by Facebook (267 sessions), and Blogger (91 sessions), while Twitter, Google+, LinkedIn and VKontakte have generated 32 sessions altogether.

The following table presents the list of the 10 most viewed pages of the website in the second half of the project:

Table 7. List of the most viewed pages of the OIKONET website (March 1, 2015 – May 31, 2016) (source: Google Analytics)

Page ?	Pageviews ? ↓
	29,422 % of Total: 100.00% (29,422)
1. /	9,386 (31.90%)
2. /admin_controller/index	1,502 (5.11%)
3. /admin_controller/project	1,071 (3.64%)
4. /admin_controller/workshops	1,011 (3.44%)
5. /index.php/admin_controller/workshops	679 (2.31%)
6. /admin_controller/partners	625 (2.12%)
7. /admin_controller/activities	623 (2.12%)
8. /admin_controller/conferences	596 (2.03%)
9. /index.php/admin_controller/index	591 (2.01%)
10. /index.php/admin_controller/project	538 (1.83%)

4.2 OIKONET blogs

During the project, eight blogs related to the OIKONET project have been opened: three blogs for the three International conferences, three blogs for the three International workshops, one blog to support the discussion about the Housing research readers, and one blog for the Community participation actions.

4.2.1 The blogs of the International Workshops

Three blogs were opened during the OIKONET project for the three International workshops:

1. Lisbon workshop: <http://oikonet-lisbonworkshop.blogspot.ch/>
2. Cottbus workshop: <http://oikonet-cottbusworkshop.blogspot.ch/>
3. Belgrade workshop: <http://oikonet-belgradeworkshop.blogspot.ch/>

The three blogs had basically the same functions and were used for similar activities: announcing the workshops, giving some practical information to the workshops' participants (e.g., about the groups, the tutors, and so on), and allowing the students to publish their works created during the workshops and – in two cases – to get the teachers' feedback.

4.2.1.1 The blog of the Lisbon Workshop

This blog was used before, during and after the workshop, as an environment where to publish news and information about the workshop and as a tool for students to present the results of their group works, which were then commented by teachers. It was also used by teachers to evaluate the student works, adding their comments as posts.

96 posts were published in the blog, 2 in the week before the workshop, 94 during the workshop itself.

76 of the 96 posts were published by the 4 groups of students to present their works; the

remaining 20 posts contained pictures related to the workshops (site visits, students at work, and so on) and general information about the workshop itself.

The following table reports the number of posts published and comments received by each group:

Table 6. Number of posts published and comments received by the 4 groups of students on the OIKONET blog during the Lisbon workshop.

Group	Posts	Comments received
A	27	21
B	19	14
C	13	19
D	17	15
Total	76	69

Comments to students' works were posted by **10 teachers**, who contributed in different measures: 2 of them commented only on 1 post, whereas one contributed with 17 comments.

4.2.1.2 The blog of the Cottbus Workshop

Like for the Lisbon workshop, also the blog of the Cottbus workshop was used before, during and after the workshop, as an environment where to publish news and information about the workshop and as a tool for students to present the results of their group works, which were then commented by teachers.

39 posts were published in the blog, 28 in the week of the workshop, 11 in July, i.e., one month after the end of the workshop.

34 of the 39 posts were published by the 11 groups of students to present their works; the remaining 4 posts contained general information about the workshop itself and suggestions by the teachers.

The following table reports the number of posts published and comments received by each group:

Table 7. Number of posts published and comments received by the 11 groups of students on the OIKONET blog during the Cottbus workshop.

Group	Posts	Comments received
1	6	4
2	2	1
3	1	0
4	6	5
5	1	1
6	3	0
7	3	1
8	3	2
9	2	0
10	5	1
11	2	0
Total	34	15

Comments to students' works were posted by **5 teachers**, who contributed in different measures: 2 of them contributed with 6 comments, the remaining 3 with 1 comment.

4.2.1.3 The blog of the Belgrade Workshop

The blog of the Belgrade workshop was used before and during the workshop, as an environment where to publish news and information about the workshop and as a tool for students to publish the results of their group works, which – unlike the previous workshops – were not commented by teachers in the blog.

22 posts were published in the blog, **21 by the 10 groups of students** to present their works (both the interim and the final works), 1 by the project's account to announce and introduce the workshop.

4.2.2 The blogs of the International Conferences

Three blogs were opened during the OIKONET project for the three international conferences:

1. Barcelona international conference: <http://oikonet-conference-barcelona.blogspot.ch/>
2. Bratislava international conference: <http://oikonet-conference-bratislava.blogspot.ch/>
3. Manchester international conference: <http://oikonet-conference-manchester.blogspot.ch/>

These three blogs were used as information websites where to announce and present the conferences, rather than as “real” blogs, where to have visitors interact and stimulate discussions. In these blogs the necessary information related to the conferences were published, such as the calls for papers, the deadlines, the conferences' programs, information about the keynote speakers, about the venues, and so on.

4.2.3 Other blogs

One blog was created by the sub-network **Research**, to stimulate the discussions and get the

comments of the project partners about the **two issues of the OIKONET Reader**: <https://oikonet.wordpress.com/>. The blog consists of two posts, where the two issues of the Reader are published and commented:

1. The first post / issue was published on September 2014, and collected **23 comments / thoughts** made by 11 project partners between March and November 2015;
2. The second post / issue was published on December 2015, and collected **18 comments / thoughts** made by 10 project partners between February and May 2016.

One blog was created by the sub-network **Community participation**, to report on the participatory activities carried out during the project, specifically the activities in Barcelona, Rimini, Bratislava and Skopje: <http://oikonet-communityparticipation.blogspot.ch/>. The blog was published in 2013, and received **22 posts**. As the goal of the blog was to present the participatory activities, and not to stimulate discussions, no comments were published in this blog.

4.3 OIKONET newsletter

During the three years of the project, five regular issues of the OIKONET newsletters have been published, starting from March 2014 up to May 2016.

1. The **first issue** was sent to **70 recipients**: 40 of them opened it (57.1%), 9 of them (12.9%) clicked on it to access further information, for a total of **26 clicks** on the links contained in the newsletter. The most clicked link was that to the homepage of the OIKONET website (8 clicks), followed by the program of the Lisbon workshop (5 clicks).
2. The **second issue** was sent to **178 recipients**: 94 of them opened it (52.8%), 28 of them (15.7%) clicked on it to access further information, for a total of **133 clicks** on the links contained in the newsletter. The most clicked link was that to the poster of the Barcelona conference (57 clicks), followed by the program of the same conference (18 clicks), the Oikopedia (11 clicks), the OIKONET YouTube channel (8 clicks), and the blog of the Lisbon workshop (7 recipients accessed it through the newsletter).
3. The **third issue** was sent to **207 recipients**: 105 of them opened it (51.2%), 15 of them (7.3%) clicked on it to access further information, for a total of **28 clicks** on the links contained in the newsletter. The most clicked links were those to the blog of the Bratislava conference: the link to the page with the instructions for submission was clicked 11 times, the link to the registration page was clicked 4 times.
4. The **fourth issue** was sent to **265 recipients**: 110 of them opened it (42.5%), 19 of them (7.3%) clicked on it to access further information, for a total of **37 clicks** on the links contained in the newsletter. The most clicked links were those to the blog of the Bratislava conference and to the OIKONET YouTube channel (7 clicks each), followed by the link to the blog of the Cottbus workshop (6 clicks).
5. The **fifth issue** was sent to **312 recipients**: 125 of them opened it (40.2%), 20 of them (6.4%) clicked on it to access further information, for a total of **28 clicks** on the links contained in the newsletter. The most clicked links were those to the OIKONET page on Facebook and to the news on the Manchester conference on the UCLAN website (4 clicks each), followed by the links to the MOOC introductory video on the OIKONET YouTube channel and to the blog of the Manchester conference (3 clicks each).

Furthermore, four **special issues** of the newsletter were sent to announce the three International

conferences:

1. The issue about the **Barcelona conference** was sent in June 2014 to **70 recipients**: 48 of them opened it (68.6%), 13 of them (18.6%) clicked on it to access further information, for a total of **65 clicks** on the links contained in the newsletter. The most clicked link was that to the program of the Barcelona conference (51 clicks).
2. The issue about the **Bratislava conference** was sent in March 2015 to **192 recipients**: 119 of them opened it (62%), 19 of them (9.9%) clicked on it to access further information, for a total of **178 clicks** on the links contained in the newsletter. The most clicked link was that to the webpage of the OIKONET project website (89 clicks), followed by the blog of the Bratislava conference (86 clicks).
3. Two issues of the newsletter were sent to announce the **Manchester conference**, in December 2015 and February 2016, respectively. The two issues were sent to **262 and 263 recipients**; they have been opened by 114 (44.0%) and 111 (42.5%) recipients, respectively; they have been clicked by 15 (5.8%) and 19 (7.3%) of them, for a total of **30 and 40 clicks** on the links contained in the newsletters. The most clicked link was in both issues the link to the blog of the Manchester conference (21 and 16 clicks, respectively).

The following table provides an overview of the opening and clicking ratio of the three issues of the OIKONET newsletter:

Table 8. Opening and clicking ratio of the OIKONET newsletter

Issue	Recipients	Opened	Clicked	Clicks
1 – March 2014	70	57.1%	12.9%	26
Special issue – Barcelona conference (June 2014)	70	68.6%	18.6%	65
2 – September 2014	178	52.2%	14.6%	93
Special issue – Bratislava conference (March 2015)	192	62.0%	9.9%	178
3 – April 2015	207	51.2%	7.3%	28
4 – October 2015	265	42.5%	7.3%	37
Special issue – Manchester conference (December 2015)	262	44.0%	5.8%	31
Special issue – Manchester conference (February 2016)	263	42.5%	7.3%	40
5 – May 2016	312	40.2%	6.4%	28

From the answers to the questions about the newsletter in the on-line survey, it emerged that 10 respondents (40%) fully read the received newsletters, 12 (48%) read them partially, while 3 respondents (12%) did not read the newsletters at all. 7 respondents (28%) forwarded at least one issue of the newsletter to a colleague.

One respondent found the newsletters helpful to have a brief overview of the activities that are part of the programme. Other partners suggested to better design the material and to have more

real life stories and more illustrative materials to present and explain the project activities.

4.4 OIKONET Facebook page and groups

The OIKONET Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/oikonet>) was created on January 15, 2014 and published at the beginning of March 2014. At the end of the project (September 30, 2016), the page had **332 likes**.

Figures 6-7. “Likes” on the OIKONET Facebook page (March 25, 2014 – February 28, 2015 and March 1, 2015 – September 30, 2016) (source: Facebook Insights).

As of September 30, 2016, **159 posts** were published on the OIKONET Facebook page. The posts received **623 likes** overall (3.9 likes per post on average); 39 of them have been shared (72 shares in total), 13 of them have been commented (16 comments in total). Each post has reached on average 141 users (i.e., each post has been shown on average to 141 users), has been visualized on average 338 times, and has engaged on average 12 users (i.e., each post has been clicked or liked or commented or shared on average by 13 users).

All Posts Published							
Search...		Reach: Organic/Paid		Post Clicks		Reactions, comments & shares	
Published	Post	Type	Targeting	Reach	Engagement	Promote	
10/08/2016 10:22	7 Cities Transforming Their Rivers From Blights to Beauties			814	56 2		
23/09/2016 10:30	OIKONET network meeting			265	48 10		
23/09/2016 18:51	Closing session of the third international OIKONET conference -			114	20 9		
23/09/2016 13:24	Vasco Rato on LCA - 3rd OIKONET conference...			198	18 2		
23/09/2016 16:45	Third OIKONET conference - afternoon session in Michelangelo			40	15 2		
23/09/2016 10:36	Third Oikonet Conference, University of Central Lancashire GL			115	13 8		
23/09/2016 01:39	Last OIKONET general meeting, Manchester...			48	12 3		
20/09/2016 12:08	On Wednesday 14, 2016 it starts the second edition of the THIN			253	10 17		
23/09/2016 12:51	A bit of technical problems ;-) ...			232	10 0		
23/09/2016 14:56	OIKONET conference - enjoying lunch break...			42	10 4		
22/09/2016 19:32	Meeting of the network in MCR. Celebrating the values of OIKO			254	9 8		
23/09/2016 12:49	Sandra Treja about the liveability of historical cities...			232	9 0		
13/09/2016 21:07	OIKONET shared Architizer's post			55	4 2		

Figure 8. List of the last posts published on the OIKONET Facebook page, ordered by number of clicks on post (source: Facebook Insights).

The activity on the Facebook page had some **peaks in specific moments**, specifically when the main project events took place, like the three international conferences, or when other specific events happened, like the publication of one issue of the newsletter.

In addition, **9 Facebook groups** related to the OIKONET project have been created:

- OIKONET – WP4 Pedagogy (<https://www.facebook.com/groups/516638171803104/>)
- OIKONET Learning Activities (<https://www.facebook.com/groups/1454779051459080/>)

- OIKONET: Habitat Regeneration Strategies
(<https://www.facebook.com/groups/716510478414701/>)
- Oikonet Lisbon Workshop (<https://www.facebook.com/groups/604185959696201/>)
- Oikodomos Threshold Matters
(<https://www.facebook.com/groups/230102717187170/?fref=ts>)
- OIKOnet Workshop Cottbus 2015
(<https://www.facebook.com/groups/1513432715565909/?fref=ts>)
- OIKONET Workshop Belgrade 2016
(<https://www.facebook.com/groups/870715703054392/>)
- OIKONET_small is power
(<https://www.facebook.com/groups/615745728566331/>)
- OIKONET_URBAN SYSTEMS
(<https://www.facebook.com/groups/1595220687460206/>)

All these are closed groups, with the exception of the last two groups, which are public.

At the end of the project, the first group (**OIKONET – WP4 PEDAGOGY**) had **32 members**; it was created on August 11, 2014, in order to foster communication and knowledge exchange among the members of the sub-network WP4 (Pedagogy), in a less formal way. As of September 30, 2016, **35 posts** were published in the group page by 6 different members; the posts received 137 likes (3.9 likes per post on average) and 8 comments.

The second group (**OIKONET Learning Activities**) was created on August 21, 2014. As it had the same goal of the first group, it was soon merged into it.

The group **OIKONET: Habitat Regeneration Strategies** was created on July 25, 2014 and at the end of the project had **117 members**. The group aims at supporting the development of the Learning Space on “Habitat Regeneration Strategies”, which was run together by different project partners as part of WP4. As of September 30, 2016, **88 posts** were published by 16 different group members (teachers and students of the Learning Space); the posts received 224 likes (2.5 likes per post on average) and 30 comments.

The group **OIKONET Lisbon Workshop** was created on July 15, 2014, and at the end of the project had **61 members**. Aim of the group was to support the teaching and learning activities of the Lisbon Workshop. The activities in the group have been high during the Lisbon workshop, but have continued also after it, until the end of the project: as of September 30, 2016, **42 posts** were published in the group page by **12 different group members**; the posts received 230 likes (5.5 likes per post on average) and 32 comments.

The group **OIKONET Threshold Matters** is a private group that was created on April 24, 2014, and at the end of the project had **67 members**. The group aims at supporting the activities of the Learning Space “Threshold Matters”, which is run together by different project partners as part of WP4. As of September 30, 2016, **122 posts** were published in the group by **17 different group members**; the posts received 206 likes (1.7 likes per post on average) and 85 comments.

The group **OIKONET Workshop Cottbus 2015** was created on September 30, 2014, and at the end of the project had **89 members**. Aim of the group is to share information among project partners about the preparation and organization of the annual OIKOnet workshop that was held in Cottbus in June 2015, and to support the teaching and learning activities of the workshop. As of September 30, 2016, **113 posts** were published in the group by **33 group members** (teachers and students of the workshop); the posts received 735 likes (6.5 likes per post on

average) and 113 comments.

The group **OIKONET Workshop Belgrade 2016** was created on April 6, 2016, and at the end of the project had **105 members**. Aim of the group is to share information among project partners about the preparation and organization of the annual OIKONET workshop that was held in Belgrade in June 2016, and to support the teaching and learning activities of the workshop. As of September 30, 2016, **216 posts** were published in the group by **40 group members**; the posts received 1933 likes (8.95 likes per post on average) and 128 comments.

The group **OIKONET_small is power** was created on September 25, 2015 and at the end of the project had **36 members**. The group aims at supporting the development of the Learning Space on “Small is power”, which was run together by different project partners as part of WP4. As of September 30, 2016, **108 posts** were published by 17 different group members (teachers and students of the Learning Space); the posts received 242 likes (2.24 likes per post on average) and 122 comments.

The group **OIKONET_URBAN SYSTEMS** was created on November 5, 2015 and at the end of the project had **10 members**. The group aims at supporting the development of the Learning Space on “Urban systems”, which was run together by different project partners as part of WP4. As of September 30, 2016, **5 posts** were published by 1 group member, which received 1 comment.

Finally, it has to be mentioned that some students participating in the OIKONET international workshops created spontaneously some Facebook groups as spaces where to communicate and interact with their groupmates; during the Belgrade workshop, for instance, 4 of these groups were created.

4.5 OIKONET Twitter channel

The Twitter channel of the OIKONET project (<https://twitter.com/OikonetOrg>) was opened on July 14, 2014. On September 30, 2016, the channel was following 35 users and had 116 followers.

As of September 30, 2016, **209 tweets** were published on the channel, 52 of which were retweets of other users. 76 tweets have been retweeted at least once (113 retweets in total, 0.54 retweets on average per tweet); 70 tweets have also been favorited (114 total favourites, 0.55 favourites on average per tweet).

The activity on the OIKONET Twitter channel in the project has been mainly generated around the major project events:

- 69 tweets were published during or immediately after the **Lisbon workshop**;
- 11 tweets were related to the **Barcelona Conference**;
- 11 tweets were related to the **Cottbus workshop**;
- 15 tweets were related to the **Bratislava conference** or general meeting;
- 25 tweets were related to the **Belgrade workshop**;
- 12 tweets were related to the **Manchester conference** or general meeting;
- 20 tweets from 9 different users used the **hashtag #OIKOconf**, 43 tweets from 4 different users used the **hashtag #OikoWorkshop**.

Finally, the hashtag **#oikonet** has been used **117 times** by **16 different users** during the project.

Three other Twitter channels related to three Learning spaces were opened in 2014: **Threshold matters** (<https://twitter.com/ThresholdMatter>), **Habitat Regeneration** (<https://twitter.com/HabRegStrat>), **Housing systems** (https://twitter.com/Housing_Systems). However, only the first one was used during the corresponding learning experience: opened on October 17, 2014, at the end of the project, the channel **Threshold matters** was following 53 users and was followed by 35; **26 tweets** were published, which were retweeted 8 times and favorited 4 times.

4.6 OIKONET YouTube channel

The OIKONET channel on YouTube was opened on April 11, 2014 (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCAPmyERBPcDY9LZbLSDVixg>). On September 30, 2016, the channel had **31 subscribers** and **48 videos** published. 18 of them were related to the first International Conference in Barcelona, 14 to the second International Conference in Bratislava, 6 to the “Thinking Dwelling” program, 4 to the Learning Space “Civic Housing”, 3 to the Lisbon workshop and to the corresponding preparatory Learning Space, 1 each to the Cottbus workshop and to the participatory actions in Rimini and Bratislava. By September 30, 2016, the 48 videos had received **3374 views**, which means an **average of 70.3 views** per video. However, huge differences can be noticed in the views for each video: 14 of them received less than 20 views, while 10 received more than 100 views. The two most viewed video are the one about the preparatory Learning Space for the Lisbon workshop (359 views) and the video that summarizes the pedagogic experience of the seminar “Civic housing” (519 views).

The following graph shows the number of views for each video, disposed in chronological order of publication:

4.7 OIKONET Google+ community

The OIKONET community on Google+ (<https://plus.google.com/u/0/communities/107770894835201140122>) was created on January 13, 2014, and at the end of the project had **34 members**. The community has not been active since June 2015. Aim of the Google+ OIKONET community is to provide a communication platform for the exchange of messages and information among the members of the project.

As of September 30, 2016, **29 posts** were published in the community by 5 different members, including 10 photos and 3 events; 7 of the 29 posts received one or more comments.

Although not formally connected to the OIKONET project, it is worth mentioning here that one of the project partners used Google+ as the online platform for the course he taught in his university, with the aim of communicating course content and feedback and of sharing problems, ideas and results among the students participating in the course. His experience with this course was presented at the Barcelona International Conference in September 2014.

5 USABILITY ANALYSIS OF THE OIKONET WEB PORTAL

Goal of the usability evaluation was to detect some of the possible problems and obstacles that may hinder visitors of the OIKONET web portal (www.oikonet.org) in achieving their goals.

The usability evaluation was made through activities of user testing: users (in this case teachers and/or researchers in the field of Architecture or Urban Design) were asked to perform some real tasks on the OIKONET web portal, while an OIKONET project partner acted as expert/inspector monitoring them and evaluating if they could complete the assigned tasks.

The evaluation team created 13 different tasks that could be accomplished on the OIKONET web portal. During the general meeting in Bratislava at the end of September 2015, the USI evaluation team presented the procedure for the usability test to all partners. The goal was that each partner would carry out at least one usability test with a colleague at his/her institution. A document with the procedure to follow and the presented tasks was distributed via e-mail to all partners.

A total of 34 usability tests, from 27 different partner institutions have been carried out in this way. Furthermore, the USI evaluation team carried out 5 usability tests using an eye-tracking tool: the users were asked to solve the same tasks as in the normal usability test, while a hardware was tracking their eye movements, allowing to understand which areas of the website were looked at mostly and where users were looking in order to find specific information to solve their tasks.

5.1 Main results of the usability test

The results of the usability analysis have been published in a dedicated report that can be found in the Appendix section of Deliverable 5.1 “Digital platform”. The report explains in detail also the adopted procedure, and includes the document with the procedure that was distributed to all partners.

We report here only the following table, which gives an overview of the tasks, of their completion and of the users’ satisfaction in accomplishing them, and the main issues that emerged from the analysis.

Task	Nr. Resp.	Not compl. / with help	Avg. Satisf.
T1: Search information about the program of activities “ thinking dwelling ”	39	2 / 1	3.62
T2: Search the term “Gentrification” in the “ OIKOPEDIA ”	39	1 / 1	3.26
T3: Search info about the outcomes of the participatory action in Rimini (specifically a Video)	39	5 / 0	3.36
T4: Search the description of the participatory action in Bratislava in the blog "Community Participation"	39	5 / 0	3.63

T5: Search the contact of the leader of WP2 (Housing Research)	39	5 / 3	3.54
T6: Go to the OIKONET Facebook page and search for infos about the "Housing design" MOOC: Is it still running? When will it finish? Can I still enroll?	33	17 / 1	2.03
T7: Search infos about the Learning Space "Threshold Matters": Is it still active? Which are the partners involved?	38	0 / 1	3.66
T8: Search the video of the keynote speech of Ekim Tan at the Barcelona conference	38	4 / 1	4.13
T9: Go to the OIKONETWORK	38	2 / 0	4.55
T10: Within the OIKONETWORK search the document presenting the international workshop held in Cottbus last June	37	2 / 1	3.76
T11: Within OIKONETWORK look for the news related to WP2 (Housing Research)	37	1 / 1	3.30
T12: Within OIKONETWORK look for information on research activities on "Resettlement": who is working on it? Which other themes / subthemes are connected to it?	38	2 / 0	3.42
T13: Go back to the OIKONET website and search the last issue of the newsletter & try to subscribe	37	0 / 0	4.62

The main general issues that emerged from the usability analysis are summarized here around the following major dimensions:

Homepage: it is overwhelming; there is too much text and content, and the font is too small to read it well (especially when reading it on smaller monitors).

Content / Structure: the structure of the website is not very clear: an introduction to the project and some explanation on how the website is structured is missing; some contents are duplicated (e.g., the same activities can be found in different sections of the website, such as in the menu section "Activities", in the recent news, and in the different tiles).

Navigation: in the horizontal menu on the top there are too many options, some of them could be merged; furthermore, the 1st level menu is not well visible, as the text font is very small and the colour is grey (the same holds for the vertical menu on the right). Instead of 2nd level menu, drop-down sub-menu lists could be created. It is confusing that on the homepage, the 1st and 2nd level menus are divided by a banner. The lateral menu was understood as an active part of the homepage and not as menu; for this reason, many users oversee the menu options when looking for content.

Search option: in the whole website there is no search option, which makes it very difficult

to find specific information.

Target audience / Involvement: it is not clear to whom the website is addressed. “Call to actions” are missing (e.g. “be part of”, “participate in conference”): the website seems more an archive of past activities, which does not incentive external people to participate in the network.

Remarks on the website as a whole: there is a lot of focus on “network” but you cannot see any people on the website. Important content does not stand out to be spotted.

Visual appeal / Layout: the look & feel of the website is pleasant.

According to the findings emerged from the usability analysis, the OIKONET web portal has been refined and upgraded (see D5.1).

6 CONCLUSIONS

From the results of the online survey and from the analysis of the actual usages of the used communication and document sharing tools it is possible to draw some conclusions about the effectiveness of these tools during the three years of the project.

In the first part of the project, some **critical issues** emerged with regard to internal communication and information sharing:

- 1) **Too many different tools** were in use, and sometimes it was not clear which tool was used for which function: it was suggested that fewer tools were selected and that for each tool it was clearly specified what it was used for.
- 2) Some partners had **problems with Dropbox**, because of the storage size limit of their accounts and because of technical problems in accessing it from their office. At the end of February 2015, this problem was addressed by **switching from Dropbox to Sharepoint**.

When it comes to communication and collaboration with colleagues and students in specific tasks (e.g., teaching and learning activities), **several good practices** emerged during the three years of the project. For instance, the **blogs related to the first two international workshops (Lisbon and Cottbus)**, which were used as a space where students had to present their work and then received feedbacks from teachers, were a successful experience. Also the use of **Facebook groups** (and, in a few cases, of a **Twitter channel**) **to support the learning activities** and the communications and interactions between teachers and students in some Learning Spaces has been a positive experience: for instance, the **Learning Spaces “Threshold Matters”, “Habitat Regeneration Strategies”, and “Small is power”** have extensively used a Facebook group, and “Threshold matters” also a Twitter channel.

With regard to the dissemination of the project activities both good practices and critical issues emerged. On the one side, for instance, some **videos on YouTube** had a **high number of views**, and **during the main project’s events** (e.g. international workshops and international conferences) **peaks in traffic and engagement** within different channels (website, Facebook page) could be observed. On the other side, **social networks have been used only in a limited way and only by some partners**, although they are generally **acknowledged as useful** tools for promotion and dissemination activities: while **Facebook has been used quite extensively** along the project as a dissemination and promotion tool, the **use of Twitter has been very limited**, and the **Google+ community has been dismissed** after the second year of the project.

Finally, the **usability analysis** that has been conducted on the OIKONET website at the end of the second year of the project was also useful to **identify some critical aspects of the web communication** of the project, such as the lack of a search option, the excessive amount of textual information available on the homepage, the content structure that in some cases was not clear, and others; the findings of the analysis helped the website administrators **refine and update the website**.